

REproducible ANALYSIS platform

REANA is ...

an analysis platform to turn any pipeline or data analysis into a **reproducible workflow**.

Simple setup

Install a client and write a yaml file, which will capture the structure of the workflow.

The yaml file ...

describes the input and output data, the computational environment, and the analysis steps.

What else?

Workflows can also be opened in interactive mode: opens a JupyterLab interface with several tools.

Fact sheet

- REANA is an open source reproducible data analysis platform, provided by CERN (<https://reana.io/>) and further developed and integrated in the PUNCH infrastructure (<https://reana-p4n.aip.de/>).
- It is a full workflow engine as it takes care of user authentication and workflow verification and execution, including the computational environment, algorithm(s), and data input/output of the performed analysis.
- The PUNCH instance can directly access the Compute4PUNCH and Storage4PUNCH federated resources, making it very flexible and scalable.
- To convert a data analysis or pipeline into a REANA workflow, it is sufficient to write a simple yaml file which describes the input and output data, the computational environment (in the form of a Docker image), and all the steps needed for the analysis.
- Important access tokens and keys can be safely stored as REANA secrets and be recollected in the workflows as environmental variables.
- Each workflow can be also opened in interactive mode, which creates a Jupyter notebook (or a full JupyterLab interface) to modify and test the code.
- Examples for creating workflows using the PUNCH4NFDI resources and REANA are available at: https://gitlab-p4n.aip.de/punch_public/reana/tutorials

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